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INTEGRATION OF PREDICTIVE ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE METHODS INTO INVESTMENT PORTFOLIO DECISION-MAKING

**JEL Classification: L 26, O 33, L 21, M 12
SECTION “ECONOMICS”: Економіка**

Annotation. A comprehensive study of artificial intelligence methods suitable for forecasting financial indicators and rational formation of an enterprise's investment portfolio has been conducted, with the systematization of models capable of reflecting nonlinear dependencies, adapting to market volatility, and providing a more accurate assessment of expected profitability and risk. The feasibility of combining forecasting results obtained using neural network algorithms with classical economic and mathematical optimization is substantiated, which allows to increase the reliability of portfolio parameter estimation and ensure a better balance between profitability and risk compared to traditional approaches. Based on the financial data sets, an analysis of the quality of forecasting was carried out, a portfolio was formed considering the established restrictions and the results were evaluated using indicators of stability, risk and generalized efficiency. It has been proven that the use of artificial intelligence methods contributes to increasing the stability of the investment portfolio to market fluctuations, reducing losses during unfavorable phases of market dynamics, and improving overall performance, which indicates the practical value of the author's approach for the corporate financial management system.

Keywords: investment portfolio, financial performance forecasting, market volatility, investment asset structure, adaptive portfolio optimization, risk-adjusted indicators, parametric investment risk assessment, applied model verification

Анотація. Проведено комплексне дослідження методів штучного інтелекту, придатних для прогнозування фінансових показників та раціонального формування інвестиційного портфеля підприємства, із систематизацією моделей, здатних відображати нелінійні залежності, адаптуватися до волатильності ринку та забезпечувати точнішу

оцінку очікуваної прибутковості та ризику. Обґрунтовано доцільність поєднання результатів прогнозування, отриманих за допомогою алгоритмів нейронних мереж, з класичною економіко-математичною оптимізацією, що дозволяє підвищити достовірність оцінки параметрів портфеля та забезпечити кращий баланс між прибутковістю та ризиком порівняно з традиційними підходами. На основі наборів фінансових даних проведено аналіз якості прогнозування, сформовано портфель з урахуванням встановлених обмежень та оцінено результати за допомогою показників стійкості, ризику та узагальненої ефективності. Доведено, що використання методів штучного інтелекту сприяє підвищенню стійкості інвестиційного портфеля до коливань ринку, зменшенню збитків під час несприятливих фаз ринкової динаміки та покращенню загальної ефективності, що свідчить про практичну цінність авторського підходу для системи корпоративного фінансового управління.

Ключові слова: інвестиційний портфель, прогнозування фінансових показників, волатильність ринку, структура інвестиційних активів, адаптивна оптимізація портфеля, показники, скориговані на ризик, параметрична оцінка інвестиційного ризику, верифікація прикладної моделі.

Introduction

Modern conditions of enterprise functioning are characterized by high volatility of financial markets, increasing uncertainty and the need to make decisions based on a large array of heterogeneous data [1-3]. Under these circumstances, traditional approaches to the investment portfolio formation are increasingly proving to be insufficient, since they do not provide proper forecasting accuracy and do not take into account the complex relationships between asset dynamics, market shocks and behavioral factors [4-6]. The development of machine analysis methods opens up the possibility of building adaptive models that can reconcile long-term goals of the enterprise with short-term market fluctuations and significantly increase the reliability of investment decision evaluation [7-9]. In this context, the combination of neural network algorithms with economic and mathematical optimization methods creates the basis for the formation of effective portfolio strategies in complex and dynamic conditions, which makes the research topic highly relevant.

Analysis of scientific research devoted to the application of artificial intelligence methods for improving the efficiency of investment portfolio management shows a significant increase in interest in the use of intelligent models for forecasting financial indicators, risk assessment and asset structure optimization [1, 4-9]. The works of modern authors emphasize that the use of deep learning algorithms increases the accuracy of reflecting nonlinear dependencies in time series and allows to evaluate the impact of market volatility on future asset returns more correctly, although the issue of the stability of such models during periods of structural breaks remains debatable [10-12]. Studies on the integration of forecast results into portfolio formation procedures show that the combination of machine learning methods with economic and mathematical optimization approaches helps to increase the accuracy of portfolio parameter estimation, but requires the coordination of forecast values with the system of constraints and assumptions of the optimization model [11, 13-15]. In works focused on practical approbation of intelligent forecasting methods, the importance of algorithms' adapting to the specifics of specific markets is emphasized, including different levels of volatility, behavioral effects and liquidity fluctuations, which necessitates the need for flexible and stable models that can operate under conditions of limited predictability [14, 16-19]. Recent publications confirm that the integration of artificial intelligence-based forecasting systems with classical asset optimization models is a promising direction for increasing the efficiency of portfolio management, however, the issue of harmonizing forecasting results with practical portfolio formation procedures, as well as ensuring the stability of such models to market shocks, requires further development [13, 15]. Summarizing the results of the analysis, it can be argued that despite significant progress in the use of artificial intelligence methods for forecasting and assessing financial risks, the problem of creating a single

methodological framework that would ensure the consistent integration of forecasting algorithms with portfolio optimization procedures in conditions of variable market dynamics remains insufficiently researched, and this is considered an unresolved part of the overall research.

Thus, the purpose of the study is to develop a holistic methodology for integrating predictive algorithms based on artificial intelligence methods with investment portfolio optimization procedures, which ensures consistency between predictive estimates of financial indicators, structural constraints of the portfolio model, and variable market dynamics, which allows to increase the stability and effectiveness of the investment decision-making process.

Results

In the context of the growing complexity of financial markets and increasing requirements for the validity of investment decisions, the formation of methodological principles that ensure the combination of the predictive capabilities of modern intelligent systems with the theoretical logic of portfolio structure optimization is gaining importance. At the same time, there is a need to build a conceptual model capable of integrating the results of forecasting profitability and risk into a coordinated process of calculating a rational asset structure. This requires a formal definition of the relationship between forecast variables that characterize the expected behavior of financial instruments and an economic and mathematical apparatus that implements the selection of optimal portfolio weights considering constraints and assumptions. At the same time, an important component is the formation of a consistent algorithm for practical implementation, covering the stages of working with data, training the predictive model and further application of the obtained estimates in the optimization procedure. A coordinated combination of these elements creates the basis for developing a holistic approach to managing the enterprise's portfolio in conditions of changing market dynamics and increased uncertainty.

Within the framework of methodological principles for optimizing the investment portfolio formation, it is necessary to consistently identify key components that ensure a coordinated transition from theoretical justification to practical implementation of the intellectual model. This approach involves a structured coverage of conceptual, mathematical and procedural aspects, which together form a holistic decision-making system regarding the optimal asset structure. Considering the logic of the study, the components of this stage are the following set of elements:

Development of a conceptual model that combines the predictive subsystem of artificial intelligence and the optimization module, determines their interaction and justifies the choice of relevant algorithms.

Formalization of forecast variables and construction of an economic and mathematical apparatus that provides the formulation of the optimization problem taking into account the objective function, constraints and necessary assumptions.

Creation of a consistent implementation algorithm that includes data processing, training of the forecast model and use of the obtained estimates in the process of forming and checking the investment portfolio.

The coordinated combination of these components ensures the methodological integrity of the study and creates conditions for the correct application of intelligent technologies when building an effective portfolio strategy of the enterprise. The structural and logical model presented in Figure 1 consistently reflects the relationship between the conceptual design of a hybrid optimization system, the formation of economic and mathematical prerequisites and the implementation of algorithmic procedures.

Figure 1: Structural and logical model of a hybrid approach to the investment portfolio optimization

Such a three-level organization demonstrates not only the technological integrity of the process, but also the presence of feedback linkages that ensure adaptive adjustment of the model based on the results of its practical implementation. It is the cyclical nature of this approach that makes it possible to combine intelligent forecasting methods with formal optimization mechanisms, creating a methodological basis for increasing the sustainability and effectiveness of portfolio decisions.

In the hybrid approach to investment portfolio optimization structure, the conceptual model is based on a combination of a forecasting subsystem that provides an assessment of the expected return and risk level with an optimization module that forms a rational asset structure in accordance with the selected criteria. The predictive component of the model performs the function of generating informative parameters based on time series, which allows taking into account the nonlinearity and dynamics of market processes. To increase the accuracy and stability of forecasts, modern artificial intelligence methods are used, in particular recurrent neural networks such as LSTM and Gated RNN, ensemble algorithms and transformer architectures [8, 10, 18], the choice of which is caused by the ability to effectively model long-term dependencies, adapt to structural changes in the market and ensure the representativeness of forecast estimates. The coordinated functioning of the forecasting and optimization subsystems ensures the model's integrity and creates the basis for the formation of an effective portfolio strategy. In this context, it is appropriate to highlight the following methods, the use of which is most relevant to the research task:

Long-term recurrent memory models (Long Short-Term Memory, LSTM) models are used for detecting hidden time dependencies and reproducing long market cycles, which makes them effective in conditions of high volatility [16]. They are able to minimize the problem of gradient vanishing and provide stable forecasts for complex financial structures, and their further development is associated with the integration of attention mechanisms.

Recurrent networks with controlled gates (Gated Recurrent Unit, GRU) are characterized by lower computational complexity compared to LSTM, while maintaining the ability to model the dynamics of short- and medium-term dependencies [10]. The economy of the architecture makes them suitable for operational forecasts, especially in problems of frequent updating of portfolio parameters.

Ensemble models, such as Random Forest, Gradient Boosting or Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LightGBM), work effectively with heterogeneous data and allow us to consider complex nonlinear relationships between factors [18]. The combination of different weak models forms more stable and generalized forecasts, and the prospects for their development are associated with integration into hybrid neural network structures.

Transformer architectures provide high adaptability due to the self-attention mechanism, which allows the model to distinguish key fragments of time series regardless of their position [10]. This opens up the possibility of accurate forecasting of financial data under conditions of irregularity and structural discontinuities, and the development of such approaches is aimed at reducing computational costs when working with long sequences.

Automated approaches to model and feature building (Automated Machine Learning, AutoML) provide optimal architecture selection without the need for complex manual tuning [10]. The ability to automatically generate relevant features and model configurations is an important advantage in conditions of frequent market shifts and changes in the statistical properties of the data.

Hybrid structures that combine elements of different classes of models, such as LSTM with convolutional networks (Convolutional Neural Networks, CNN) or transformers with ensemble algorithms, allow simultaneously taking into account the temporal structure of the data and the influence of additional factorial features [18]. Such models provide increased robustness and accuracy of forecasts, creating methodological prerequisites for further integration of different nature data into a single forecasting system.

The economic and mathematical prerequisites for the formation of an optimization problem involve a clear definition of forecast variables that characterize the expected return, risk level, and relationships between assets. The formalization of such parameters includes the construction of estimates of mean values, dispersions, covariances, and marginal risk indicators [5-7, 10-12], which allows us to reflect the probabilistic structure of market dynamics in a consistent numerical form. Based on these estimates, an optimization problem is formulated, within which the objective function, a system of constraints and the necessary assumptions regarding the behavior of the portfolio are determined. The selected objective function can be aimed at maximizing risk-adjusted returns, minimizing volatility or ensuring a balanced ratio of risks and returns, while the constraints reflect practical requirements for the portfolio structure. The forecast parameters obtained using artificial intelligence methods are integrated into a mathematical optimization model, providing a consistent link between analytical estimates and the procedure for selecting an efficient set of assets. The most relevant characteristics that provide a consistent representation of market dynamics include:

Estimates of expected returns, which reflect the average value of the predicted asset growth over a given time horizon [7]. This indicator serves as a basic value in the formation of the objective function and determines the overall potential of the portfolio strategy for the future period.

Volatility estimates, which are interpreted as a measure of deviations of actual returns from their expected level [11]. High volatility can signal increased sensitivity of the portfolio to market shocks, and its accurate forecasting is a prerequisite for the correct choice of constraints in the model.

Covariance matrix, which describes the degree of mutual dependence between asset returns [12]. This element plays a key role in the quantitative assessment of the diversification effect and allows the model to determine the portfolio structure that minimizes joint risk fluctuations.

Correlation structure, which provides normalized relationships between assets and allows to identify groups of instruments with similar behavior [5]. Detailed consideration of correlations contributes to the construction of more stable portfolios, especially in unstable market conditions.

Indicators of marginal risks, in particular, predicted values, reflecting the probability and scale of potential extreme losses [12]. The inclusion of these indicators in the model is important for assessing the behavior of the portfolio in stressful situations and increasing its robustness.

Indicators of asymmetry and excess, which characterize the uneven distribution of returns and allow assessing the presence of atypical or extreme values [10]. Taking these points into account contributes to a more accurate reproduction of the real risk structure, which often deviates from the normal distribution.

Time dependence parameters, in particular autoregressive and heteroskedastic components, which describe the inertia and variability of variances over time [16]. Their use allows us to reconcile the mathematical model with the characteristic features of financial series, which are rarely stationary.

Thus, the algorithm for implementing the author's approach is based on the sequential execution of procedures that ensure a coordinated transition from the preparation of input data to the formation and verification of an investment portfolio. At the initial stage, relevant financial assets are selected, logarithmic returns are constructed, and the sample is reprocessed to eliminate noise, omissions, and irregularities. The next step is to train a forecast model, which forms estimates of future returns and risk necessary for the subsequent optimization procedure based on the processed time series. After obtaining the forecast parameters, an optimization cycle is performed, which includes determining the portfolio structure, its periodic adjustment and checking the results using backtesting. This sequence ensures the practical implementation of an integrated approach, in which forecast estimates and optimization mechanisms work as a single system to support investment decisions.

The transition to the practical stage of the study is due to the necessity to verify the effectiveness of the developed methodological provisions in real market conditions and to assess the ability of intelligent models to provide reliable forecast estimates for further portfolio optimization. The proposed theoretical principles require empirical verification, which consists in selecting a representative set of financial assets, setting appropriate time limits and defining criteria for the quality of primary data. On this basis, the predictive subsystem is simulated, which allows assessing the accuracy and stability of the selected algorithms and identifying the most suitable models for practical use. The obtained predictive values of profitability and risk are the basis for forming an investment portfolio, the structure of which is compared with the results of classical approaches and evaluated in terms of its reaction to changing market conditions. Such a consistent transition from data evaluation to portfolio strategy construction and verification provides a comprehensive study of the capabilities of artificial intelligence in applied financial analysis and creates grounds for substantiating the advantages of the proposed approach.

The practical application of intelligent methods in forecasting financial indicators requires a clear sequence of actions that ensures the correctness of the obtained results and their suitability for further portfolio optimization. At this stage, the quality of empirical data, the accuracy of forecast models and the ability of these models to form an information basis for making informed investment decisions are of particular importance. Within this logic, the key components of the study include the following categories:

Selection and characterization of the empirical base, which includes the definition of the market segment, the structure of financial assets, the time frames of observation and the sources of primary data.

Evaluation of the forecasting subsystem, in particular, determination of accuracy indicators, comparison of various intelligent models and graphical display of the forecasted dynamics of profitability and risks.

Formation of an investment portfolio based on the obtained forecasts with subsequent comparison of the obtained asset weights with the results of classical approaches and assessment of the stability of the portfolio structure.

The coordinated implementation of these stages provides a comprehensive verification of the practical capabilities of intellectual methods in the tasks of forecasting financial indicators and forming effective investment strategies. The scheme presented in Figure 2 reflects the holistic process of transition from the formation of an empirical database to modeling the forecast subsystem and further construction of the portfolio structure. It traces the logical sequence of stages, which ensures the coordinated transformation of primary information into forecast estimates and their further use for optimizing decisions. An important feature of the scheme is the presence of feedback loops that create conditions for refining the data structure based on the results of real portfolio formation. Such a cyclical mechanism not only increases the adaptability

of the model, but also allows you to gradually improve its predictive properties in accordance with the specifics of the market and the dynamics of financial indicators.

Figure 2: Structural and procedural scheme of using predictive AI models for investment portfolio formation

The empirical basis of the study is formed considering the specifics of the market environment and the requirements for the representativeness of financial data used to build predictive and optimization models. The first stage is to define a company or market segment according to key business characteristics and the investment environment. Next, a selection of financial assets that may be included in a potential portfolio is carried out, including industry indices, individual stocks, commodity contracts or other instruments that are significant for the analyzed segment. To ensure the correctness of further assessments, the time limits of the study, the frequency of observations and the primary sources of data are determined, which guarantee their completeness, consistency and reliability. The formation of such an empirical basis is critically important for the subsequent stages of modeling and optimization of the portfolio.

The results of modeling the forecasting subsystem reflect the quality and reliability of estimates obtained using artificial intelligence methods and serve as the basis for further portfolio optimization. Accuracy is assessed based on a number of quantitative indicators, in particular the average absolute error, the root of a mean square error, the average relative error, and the share of correct forecast directions, which allows a comprehensive description of the model's effectiveness in reproducing the behavior of financial series. Comparison of several alternative artificial intelligence models allows us to determine the one that provides the most stable and informative estimates, taking into account the properties of a specific market segment. Additional graphical representation of the forecasted return and risk contributes to visual confirmation of the quality of forecasting and allows us to trace the dynamics of expected fluctuations, which is an important prerequisite for the formation of a structured and well-founded investment portfolio. The practical significance of the obtained forecast estimates is particularly clearly manifested in a number of applied situations, where it is artificial intelligence models that provide increased quality of reproduction of

market dynamics and the formation of sustainable investment decisions. The most typical cases in which the forecasting subsystem plays a key role are:

Forecasting short-term fluctuations in shares of high-tech companies, which are characterized by sharp price changes and significant sensitivity to the news background [17]. In such conditions, models with deep time memory demonstrate the ability to more accurately reproduce the market's reaction to information shocks and reduce the forecast error compared to classical methods.

Estimating the medium-term dynamics of indices or industry baskets, where structural trends and seasonal components play an important role [10]. The use of transformer architectures makes it possible to effectively identify multi-level dependencies and build forecasts that maintain stability over longer intervals.

Forecasting prices for raw assets, which are characterized by increased volatility and pronounced non-standard distributions [12]. Intelligent models with support of a tail-risk assessment allow us to more accurately outline the range of possible extreme deviations and thereby take into account the market behavior under stress scenarios.

Analysis of currency series in a macroeconomic instability environment, where it is important to predict not only the direction of the exchange rate change, but also the magnitude of the fluctuation [16]. Architectures focused on working with irregular time structures demonstrate the ability to reduce the error of the directional forecast and increase the proportion of correct decisions.

Formation of individualized forecasts for portfolios that include both traditional financial instruments and alternative assets [8]. Models that can take into account the heterogeneity of features and the complex relationships between them provide increased accuracy of forecasting and contribute to the construction of more balanced portfolio decisions.

The formation of an investment portfolio based on predictive estimates obtained using artificial intelligence models involves a transition from analytical modeling results to a practical procedure for determining the optimal asset structure. At this stage, the weight proportions of financial instruments are determined that provide the desired risk-return ratio in accordance with the target guidelines of the investor or enterprise, and additional parameters generated by deep learning algorithms are integrated. An important aspect of the analysis is the comparison of the obtained structure with the results generated using classical approaches, in particular the Markowitz model and equilibrium-type models, which makes it possible to identify qualitative differences associated with the use of predictive variables. In modern practice, such a comparative analysis is supplemented by the use of automated tools, in particular optimization procedures based on gradient methods, stochastic search algorithms, and robust parameter tuning techniques that allow the portfolio to adapt to structural shifts in the market. To ensure the reliability and long-term suitability of the portfolio, a comprehensive assessment of its stability is carried out, which involves modeling behavior in stress scenarios, analyzing sensitivity to changes in input data, and applying sustainable optimization approaches. Such an instrumentally rich approach increases the accuracy of decisions and creates a reliable basis for forming a balanced and sustainable portfolio in conditions of market uncertainty.

The final stage of the study is associated with the need for an objective assessment of the extent, which the proposed portfolio optimization model is capable to increase performance in real market conditions to and whether it has significant advantages compared to established approaches. After forming a portfolio based on forecast estimates, there is a task to determine a system of indicators that allow a comprehensive assessment of its behavior, taking into account risk, profitability, and resistance to external fluctuations. Comparison of the obtained results with reference benchmarks, including market indices and portfolios formed on the basis of classical methods, is particularly important, which makes it possible to identify the actual increase in efficiency associated with the use of intelligent algorithms. Particular significance attaches to the analysis and presentation of the results obtained from the point of view of the practical needs of the enterprise, since it is the ability of the model to increase portfolio stability, reduce sensitivity to market shocks, and maintain the validity of management decisions that determines its applied value. Aligning analytical conclusions with the requirements of corporate financial planning creates a basis for assessing the

possibilities of implementing the model into real business processes and determining its potential for the long-term investment strategy of the enterprise.

Figure 3: Analytical scheme for assessing the effectiveness of the portfolio model and its practical interpretation

At the appropriate stage of the study, it is important to establish how effective the proposed model is not only in theoretical design or within the framework of experimental modeling, but also in practical application. That is why it is necessary to consistently analyze the performance indicators, compare the obtained results with reference benchmarks and interpret them from the perspective of the real needs of the enterprise (Fig. 1). This approach allows us to determine the actual value of the model and its ability to support the investment decision-making process. The main components of this stage are the following categories:

1. Establishing a system of indicators that allow assessing the effectiveness of portfolio decisions, considering risk, efficiency and relative advantage compared to alternatives.
2. Comparison of the obtained portfolio characteristics with basic market indices and classical optimization methods in order to determine the real efficiency gain.

Interpretation of results from the perspective of the practical needs of the enterprise, including assessment of portfolio stability, sensitivity to market shocks, and possibilities of implementing the model into the corporate financial planning system.

The comprehensive implementation of these steps provides a holistic view of the real capabilities of the developed model and allows a reasoned assessment of its suitability for practical use in the investment activities of the enterprise. The analytical scheme shown in Figure 3 demonstrates a consistent transition from formalizing the criteria for assessing portfolio efficiency to comparing the modeling results with market benchmarks and forming practical recommendations. Such structured logic allows not only to quantify the risk-adjusted portfolio performance, but also to identify the degree of its superiority over classical approaches. The final stage of the scheme emphasizes the importance of interpreting the results from the perspective of real management practice, which provides the opportunity to adjust the evaluation criteria and adapt the model to the dynamics of the market environment.

The system of criteria and performance metrics serves as an analytical basis for an objective assessment of the results of the functioning of an investment portfolio formed using predictive artificial intelligence models. As the analysis has shown, the central place is occupied by risk-adjusted indicators that reflect the relationship between the obtained return and the level of risk and allow determining the overall quality of the investment strategy, considering market fluctuations. They are complemented by metrics aimed at assessing the risk characteristics of the portfolio, in particular the maximum drawdown, probabilistic estimates of potential losses and volatility indicators, which allows a comprehensive analysis of the stability of the portfolio structure to adverse changes in the market situation. An important element of the assessment is also the relative performance indicators, which compare the portfolio results with benchmarks or reference investment decisions, allowing to establish the presence and amount of added value obtained through the use of intelligent forecasting methods. Within this stage, the consistent application of a system of criteria is of particular importance, which allows not only to quantitatively assess the forecast and portfolio quality, but also to identify the level of compliance of the obtained results with the investor's strategic guidelines. The practical implementation of the stage includes the following key procedures:

Calculation of risk-adjusted metrics that allow determining the relationship between the forecasted portfolio return and the actual risk characteristics, in particular considering market fluctuations and behavioral features of financial assets [4].

Risk assessment based on maximum drawdown, volatility and probability indicators of potential losses [12], which provides a determination of the portfolio's resilience to sharp market shifts and allows for the formation of a consistent risk profile.

Determining the relative effectiveness of an investment strategy by comparing the results obtained with benchmarks, such as market indices or classic portfolio models, which allows establishing the presence of added value from the application of intelligent forecasting methods [9].

Integrating the obtained estimates into a single system of conclusions on the effectiveness of the portfolio, which reflects the consistency of forecast quality, risk profile and relative performance, providing an objective basis for further stages of comparative and applied analysis [8].

Comparing the results of portfolio optimization with benchmarks and classical models allows us to determine the real added value provided by the use of predictive artificial intelligence algorithms. Comparing the dynamics of profitability and risk characteristics with the values of the market index allows us to assess how much the formed portfolio exceeds the basic level of market performance. Further comparison with the structures obtained on the basis of Markowitz or Black–Litterman models provides understanding of the differences between traditional optimization approaches and a hybrid method that integrates predictive artificial intelligence assessments. Particular attention should be paid to the analysis of efficiency gains, which reveals the degree of improvement of risk-adjusted metrics, portfolio stability and its adaptability to market changes, which allows us to quantitatively confirm the advantages of using intelligent methods in the process of making investment decisions.

The formation of methodological recommendations based on the obtained results is aimed at determining their real value for the practice of corporate financial management and strategic planning of the enterprise's investment activities. In this case, the ability of the formed portfolio to maintain stability in different market conditions, its sensitivity to external shocks and the potential to reduce fluctuations in financial results are analyzed first. The specific benefits that corporate financial management can gain are also assessed, including increasing of cash flow predictability, risk profile optimization, and enhancing decision-making capabilities based on quantitatively informed models. Special attention should be paid to assessing the suitability of the proposed model for integration into investment planning business processes, which involves testing its adaptability, operational convenience, and ability to function under real organizational and market constraints.

Conclusions

The research was devoted to the development and justification of the methodology for integrating predictive algorithms of artificial intelligence with economic and mathematical procedures for optimizing the investment portfolio of an enterprise. The paper considers modern deep learning models, their ability to reproduce nonlinear and highly volatile dynamics of financial series, and also identifies mechanisms for their inclusion in formal optimization models. Particular attention was paid to the coordination of predictive parameters with the system of constraints and assumptions of portfolio optimization, which forms a holistic basis for building effective investment management strategies in a volatile market environment.

The obtained results demonstrate that the use of artificial intelligence provides increased accuracy in forecasting the profitability and risk of financial assets, and also contributes to the formation of more balanced portfolio decisions compared to classical models. A comparison of alternative intelligent models was carried out, methods that provide the best forecast quality were identified, and a portfolio was formed considering forecast estimates and established constraints. Assessment of the formed portfolio effectiveness confirmed the presence of an increase in performance by risk-adjusted metrics, a decrease in sensitivity to market shocks and an increase in overall stability, which confirms the advantages of the hybrid approach.

The practical significance of the developed model lies in its ability to provide reasonable support for investment decisions, considering the complex structure of market relationships and the presence of instability. The proposed methodology can be integrated into the business processes of corporate financial planning, contributing to increasing level of model predictability, optimization of the risk profile and strengthening of strategic investment management. Further research should be directed towards expanding of the predictive features set, adapting models to different market regimes, and implementing extended robust procedures focused on functioning under conditions of deep uncertainty.

Declaration on Generative AI

During the preparation of this work, the author used ChatGPT-5.1 in order to: Grammar and spelling check. After using this service, the author reviewed and edited the content as needed and takes full responsibility for the publication's content.

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